

Student's Performance Analysis System Using Cumulative Predictor Algorithm

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Abstract:

Election of candidates who are expected to do well academically in institutions of higher learning requires a system of admissions based on reliable and legitimate admissions criteria. This study focuses on methods for helping colleges make admissions decisions by employing data mining techniques to predict applicants' academic success in higher education. The suggested technique was validated using data collected from 1,039 scholars enrolled in the Computer Science and Information College of a Saudi public institution between 2016 and 2019. The findings show that based on several pre-admission characteristics, candidates' early university performance may be predicted before admission.

Keywords:

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Open University Learning Analytics Dataset (OULAD), Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC).

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) is one of the most wide-learning platforms. The MOOCs present the course using digital tool accoutrements in colorful forms similar as visual, audio, videotape and plaintextbook. utmost scholars prefer using videotape lectures to understand the contents of assignments over completely reading plain textbook documents. The interactive videotape in the MOOCs could reduce scholars' stress; help them to feel relaxed and learn snappily. visual, audio, video and plain text. Most students prefer using video lectures to understand the contents of lessons over thoroughly reading plain text documents. The interactive video in the MOOCs could reduce students' stress, help them to feel relaxed and learn quickly.

Connectivist Massive Open Online Courses (CMOOCs) and extended Massive Open Online Courses (eMOOCs) are the two main categories into which MOOCs may be divided. The XMOOCs are a model for learning that is based on the propositions of cognitivist behaviourism. The courses are structured similarly to a typical course, with a syllabus that includes a set of VHS lectures, a set of multiple choice quizzes, and a final exam. Daily videotape lectures with the course instructor going over the material from the previous online assignment are made available. The performers are free to watch and pause the videotape whenever they choose. Additionally, by participating in discussion forums, students can socially connect with the teacher, other students, and other performers. These discussion forums are frequently used by preceptors to submit questions, provide task results, and respond to student questions. As a result, the discussion forums are essential for improving the course's quality and creating collaborative and interesting online sessions.

The connectivist literacy hypothesis is the foundation of the CMOOCs, a new literacy model. With the connectivism method, the teacher would not provide students with factual literacy material; instead, students would ask questions and interact with other actors to learn about the course syllabus. In contrast to XMOOCs, where university lecturers can gauge the students knowledge by using computer-marked assessment feedback, it is impossible to employ MOOCs to

student completes an online evaluation, a computer immediately provides feedback. After successfully completing the course, the learner will receive their XMOOCs instrument. There is no official evaluation provided in the CMOOCs. Universities are therefore not regarded as MOOCs as approved courses

Artificial intelligence has recently emerged as an effective method in the assessment and testing of student performance in online courses due to the lightning-fast improvements in technology. Many experimenters used machine literacy to predict student achievement, but many workshops were also conducted to evaluate the performance of the circles. Preceptors were unable to cover the actual students learning wind as a result.

In this study, there are two sets of trials. Retrogression analysis is used in the initial experiments to estimate the evaluation scores of the students. In addition to past performance, the pupil's history and current conditioning are used to predict future progress. In the alternative set of trials, a machine literacy system under supervision has been used to forecast long-term student success Behavioral variables, followed by temporal and demographic information, were initially regarded the three main categories of seeker predictors. The suggested approaches let preceptors keep track of students progress in real time and provide fresh insight into identifying the most important literacy effort. To the best of our knowledge, only the success and failure of an online course have been used to measure student performance Our model uses three class cues to predict performance: success, failure, and withdrawal.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A key indicator of learning progress in a virtual literacy environment is student performance. Colorful designs have been advocated by experimenters to conceal performance. The literature review in the pertinent field is offered in this part.

The Factor Analysis Model (FAM) was created to predict how well students would perform in the Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) while taking into account the relative difficulty of assessments built on the Item Response Theory idea. The degree of association between the student's performance and the assessment questions can be inferred from the task difficulty position. A number of predictor variables, such as the number of openings given to the student at each task, the amount of time spent on each step, and the level of difficulty of each question or idle variable, are defined in the FAM in order to cypher the likelihood that a student will complete a task successfully. The findings show that adding idle variables to estimates of student performance can improve the model significantly.

The researchers discovered that Learning analyt cs (LAS) in con unct on w th ach ne

learning are efficient tools that give the capacity to trace student knowledge in order to assess how the behaviours of learners may affect their learning accomplishment in MOOCs. Researchers showed that machine learning could assist teachers in delivering cohort information about the learning process, giving them the ability to visually represent and analyse the data collected from each tier of learners. As a result these courses can help students develop an accurate predictive model.

The final performance of students in an online courses predicted using their first assessment and quiz results, together with social characteristics. There were introduced two predictive models. In the first model, pupils receipt of a normal or distinction certificate was predicted using logistic regression. Logistic regression was also utilised in the second prediction model to foretell whether or not students will receive certification. The findings showed that the quantity of peer evaluations is the key element in earning a distinction. The average quiz scores were thought to be the best indicator of who would receive a certificate: The accuracy of the distinction model was reported to be 92.6% accurate and the accuracy of the normal model to be 79.6% accurate.

III. METHODOLOGY

The University of Maryland, Baltimore County has looked into how the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) data and student performance are related (UMBC). LA made use of the technology Check My Activity (CMA) through its Implementation. CMA is a LA tool that compares students VLE activities to other activities and gives instructors regular feedback on the emotional states of their students. The findings indicated that frequent participants in the course are more likely to achieve a grade of Cor higher than non-participants. METHODOLOGY

A) Data Description

The Open University Learning Analytics Dataset (OULAD) repository is where the OULAD dataset was taken from. Between 2013 and 2014, the Open University in the UK offered undergraduate and graduate students an online course with vibrant content. Studentinfo, the primary composite table, is related to alitables. The "studentinfo" table contains data pertinent to the demographics of scholars.

gathered in the "Assessments" and "Student Assessment tables. The number, weight, and kind of assessments required for each module are listed in the "Assessments" table. The final test is usually followed by a set of assessments for each module. The tests include instructor-pronounceable tests (TMA) and computer pronounceable tests (CMA). The total of all assessments (50) and final exams (50) is used to calculate the final average grade. The "Student Assessment" table contains details about student assessment results, including the date the assessment was turned in and the grade it received. The "Assessments" and "Student Assessment tables contain information about student performance. The "Assessments" table contains a list of the number, type and weight of assessments that are necessary for each module. Usually, there are a number of evaluations for each

module after the final exam. The exams consist of computer pronounceable tests (CPT) and instructor-pronounceable tests (TMA)(CMA). The final average grade is calculated using the sum of all assessments (50) and final exams (50). The "Student Assessment" table includes information regarding the results of student assessments, such as the date the assessment was submitted and the grade it earned.

B) Feature Extraction

In our prior work, the characteristics birth was accepted. Behavior-inducing features were induced via VLE conditioning. Two features are uprooted for each student at a given time t: the number of sessions (o) and the number of clicks ((t)) (ct). The behavioural characteristics might be classified as static or dynamic.

Static Behavioral features: These are a set of behavioral features that correspond to student activities since the first time they engaged in the course till last day they quit the course. Let us consider the set $X \subset \mathbb{R}^t \wedge \wedge$, in which X , , represents the j^{th} activity of the i^{th} student at time i. S is a set of students denoted as an n-dimensional vector $[S_1, \dots, S_n]$, where n is the number of students. Furthermore, M is defined as an m-dimensional vector that represents VLE learning activity types, $M = [M_1, \dots, M_m]$, where m is the number of learning activities that the ith student is assigned.

C) Dynamic Behavioral Features: These are a set of behavioral features that vary over time. Let t be a sequence of disjointed time intervals, where $i \in [1,6]$. To represent all student activities at time t, we define the type of student's activity records as the vector $X_i = [X_{i,1}, X_{i,2}, \dots, X_{i,p}]$. Here y_i denotes learning activity that is undertaken at time i by student S_i , such that $y_i = 1, \dots, m$; where m is given as the number of learning activities. *Students performance Model*

In this case study, two sets of experiments are run. While the second experiment uses the static behavioural attributes, the first experiment uses the dynamic behavioural aspects to predict student performance.

Regression and classification are used to frame the issues. when $q \{ \{ \text{emp}_{s,1n}^o - s^o \} \} \{ \text{ocqs} \} \{ \text{uden} \} \{ \text{perfo} \} \{ \text{Jjjqnc} \} \{ \text{on} \}$

The data pertainine to student performance is

examinations, the regression option is taken into account, but the classification setting is used when attempting to forecast ultimate student achievement for the entire course. Where the target class is whether students pass, fail, or withdraw from courses, it is regarded as a multi-class problem.

Preceptors could give prompt intervention support and new literacy tools to students who have low scores with the use of prior grade vaccination. The student should participate in five CMA assessments and six TMA evaluations. In addition to the final exam, according to the preliminary talk. There is a deadline for turning in the assessments. Our temporal analysis is based on the TMA submission date because the TMA assessment imports 45 of the final outcome whereas the CMA assessment weighs only 5.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the course is then divided into six time intervals, which correspond with the due dates for submission of assessments. This means that in the first series of trials, student performance is based on timely submission of assessments. Distribution of the student behaviour records is done in accordance with the assessment date. This analysis takes into account the student's interaction behaviour and performance on earlier exams.

In the second series of studies, student behaviour was aggregated across the six time slices into a single time slice, and student performance was assessed as a result. For the second round of trials, behavioural characteristics, demographic characteristics and temporal characteristics served as the input factors.

In order to evaluate the student performance forecasting model during the course of two experiments, a number of indicators have been taken into account. In terms of regression analysis, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and R-squared (R²) are used to forecast students' assessment marks, F Measure, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC), and Area Under Curve (AUC) are utilised to take into account the accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity of the classification analysis in order to predict final student performance. Additionally, tenfold cross-validation is employed in both regression and classification analyses, with 50% of the dataset being used to train the algorithms. An additional 20% of the original, fragmented dataset was used to

evaluate the generalisation errors for unknown data.

D) **Figure 1.** Student behavioral features based on TMA intervals
Features selection

Features selection is only taken into account for the first set of experiments because our goal is to study how student performance on one assessment affects performance on the next. In this case study, recursive feature elimination (RFE) is used.

One of the most well-liked methods for wrapper feature selection is recursive feature removal. RFE is an optimization algorithm built on techniques for backwards selection and resampling. Up until there are only a few features, the model is created repeatedly. Using several components, the data set is divided into train and bootstrap samples. The algorithms are determined to be the most crucial attributes at each iteration. The most crucial predictors from the new model are kept until all are used up in order to determine the likelihood of ranking features.

Table 1 contains the findings of the feature selection over six periods. It is founded on RMSE standards. The findings show that the highest top features across all intervals are the student evaluation marks from the prior slice.

The most significant features across all intervals are "session.homepage" and "sum click.homepage" of the previous and current time slice, respectively. Additionally, it appears that only for intervals 1 and 2 "sum click forum" and "session.forumng" have been chosen as top features. Over all time intervals, the activities (homepage, quiz, subpage) provided reliable predictions of the students' grades features are employed in the second set of features.

Table 1 Features selection (RfE)

Interval	Features
Interval 1	session.homepage T2" sum click. forum T2" "session.resource T2" session.tour mug T2" sum_click.subpage.T2"
Interval 2	"Score.Assessment 1" session.homepage T3" "session.quiz T3" session.homepage T2" sum_click.torn.wanu.T3
Interval 3	"SiOrd. AsSc5sm.inl *" sum_click.homepage T3 " sum_click.subpage T 3" session.homepage T3 " "session.subpage T3"
Interval 4	"score. Assessment 3" "sum_click.quiz/T5", "session.quiz/T5", "sum_click.homepage/T5" "session.homepage/T5"
Interval 5	"score. Assessment 4", "session.qti iz T5", sum_click.quiz T5". "sc- ssion.qti iz T5 " sum_click.hoiucpazc T6"
Interval 6	"Score. Assessment 5", session.homepage T6". sum_click.homcpigc. T6", "sum_click.homcpipc T7" "scscion .lionacpazc T7"

E) Simulation results- Students Assessments Grades Model

In order to forecast students' evaluation grades over six time periods, regression analysis has been used. Results of the regression analysis are given in Table 2. Two sets of features are taken into account Dynamic behavioural features and student performance are used as predictors in the first set of features, whereas the top five features are only used in the second set of features.

In this experiment, several machine learning models are employed, such as the Random Forest (RF), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) with two hidden layers, Neural Networks with one hidden layer (Nnet), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), and Generalized Linear Model (GLM).

The empirical findings from the initial set of features have marginally outperformed the chosen features. The ML and R art in the

second set of characteristics, however, deliver superior outcomes. The RMSE metric calculates the discrepancy between expected values and observed values. The predictive model performs better as evidenced by the lowest RMSE value. RF achieves the best RMSE for the initial batch of features, with values of 8.131 over interval 3. The Gbm model has the best RMSE for the second set of characteristics, with a value of 11.230 over interval 1.

As can be observed, the GBM models for intervals 1, 2, 4, 5, and 6 yield the best RMSE, with average values of 11 to 22 for both sets of features. The second-best model is held by RF. Over all intervals, the RMSE in Gbm grew by 3% and obtained an average value of 11-23. With values of 44.904 and 39.215 at interval 6 for both sets of features, Mlp had the worst RMSE.

Table 2 Result for Predication Students' Assessments Grades Model

Interval	Features
Interval 1	1' i\ e Top 1' catu res "session.homepage T2 " su m click.fern mug T2 " "session. resource T2" "session.torning T2" sum_click.subpage T2 "
Interval 2	"Score. Assessment 1 " session.homcp3 gc T3 " "session.quiz T3" session.homepage T2" sum_click.loruinnc T3
Interval 3	"Score. Assessment 2" "sum_click.homepage/T3" "sum_click.subpage/T3" "session.homepage/T3" "session.subpage/T3"
Interval 4	"score. Assessment 3" "stim_click.qu iz TS". session.quiz T 5". sum_click.homcpattc T5". "session.homepage T5 "
Interval 5	"score. Assessment 4", "session.qti iz T5". "sum_click.quiz T5". "session.qtiiz T5" sum_click.humcDacc T6"
Interval 6	"Score. Assessment 5". session.homepage T 6". sum_click.homepage T6". sum_click.homcpattc T7" session .homepagc T 7"

F) Simulation results- Final Students Performance Model

The second experiment's categorization analysis findings are shown in the table below. In this case study, the same set of machine learning classifiers that were employed in the prior experiment are utilized.

Table 3 shows that all classifiers reach comparable 1' deal outcomes, with Gbm ach'ieving the maximum

performance with a value of 0.868 and RF, Nnet, achieving the lowest accuracy with a value of 0.854. According to Table 4, the class "Withdrawn" achieved the highest accuracy of all Classifiers, averaging 0.99, while the class "Fail" performs the worst, with an accuracy range of roughly 0.76-0.80.

The classifiers for the categories "With-draw" and "Pass" have high overall sensitivities. The values of 0.99 and 0.92 were reported by Rpart as having the highest sensitivity. All classifiers had very low sensitivities for the class "Fail." This is to be expected because there aren't many records with the goal class "Fail," therefore the algorithm can't learn well. The Gbm and Nnet offer the best results for real negative instances, with specificity=0.998 for class "Withdrawn." Rpart obtained results of 0.81 for the class "Pass" with the lowest level of specificity. The best F1-Measure obtained by GBM, as can be observed, produced values of 0.993, 0.864, and 0.772 for the classes "Withdrawn," "Pass," and "Fail," respectively. Rpart has the lowest F1 Measure, with a value of 0.67. The decision threshold value for the true and false positive rate across each class is determined in this study using ROC. ROC curves are shown in Figure 2. Total in all, AUC values for all classes ranged from 0.99 to 0.82. The demographic, behavioural, and temporal characteristics in classification analysis were merged, as was previously mentioned. The total number of variables in this model is 35. As a result, the overfitting problem may affect the prediction model. In this instance, we compare the performance of the classifiers in terms of train and test error, which may indicate an overfitting issue.

The outcome of the overfitting evaluation is shown in Figure 3. All classifiers exhibit minimal levels of training and test error, as can be seen. Gbm achieved the lowest test and train error. A comparable test mistake was acquired by the RF Nnet, with an about 14% percentage. These classifiers have slightly larger training errors. The Mip model recorded the biggest inaccuracy. Despite the fact that most classifiers fit all models well, Mlp suffers from overfitting.

Table 4 Results for Final Students Performance Prediction Model

Classifier	Performance Metrics				
	ACC.	F1	Sens.	Spec.	AUC
Rpart	0.866	0.865	0.923	0.810	0.867
Pass	0.866	0.865	0.923	0.810	0.867
Fail	0.767	0.671	0.582	0.952	0.821

Figure 2. Roc Curve

Figure 3 Comparing Computational Training and Test Time

Table 3 Accuracy of Result for Final Students Performance Prediction Model

Classifier	Accuracy
RF	0.854
Rpart	0.862
Gbm	0.868
Nnet	0.854

***, **, *

classifiers

Figure 3. Comparing Computational Training and Test Time
G. Discussion

In this case study, both regression and classification analysis are taken into account. The model's prediction of students grades reveals that the best RMSE and R2 are acquired throughout the third interval, while the poorest RMSE and R2 are displayed for intervals five and six. This may be explained by the fact that more students recorded data for interval 3 than for any other interval, which allowed the algorithm to pick up more information and improve model fit. Compared to the fewest amount of training examples displayed during interval 6.

The appropriate sensitivities and specificities for all classifiers are revealed by the final student performance predicting model. Even if all classifiers have balanced sensitivities and specificities for the classes "Withdrawn" and "Pass," the specificities are higher than the comparable sensitivities for the class "Fail." This is because the database is biased in favour of the most popular courses, "Pass" and "Withdrawn." Predicting withdrawal from the course is given higher importance than predicting success and failure in this scenario because it is more valuable to forecast students who would drop the course entirely than students who will continue to take it.

The main factor that causes machine learning models to perform better in classification than regression is the relevance of the feature set types. As a result, only dynamic behavioural data are used to estimate students assessment grades in classification analysis, whereas static behavioural features along with the temporal features and demographic features are used as input variables in the prediction of the final student performance model. The dates on which students enrolled in and dropped out of an online course are among the temporal variables that are effective indicators of

student achievement. Given that the database contains student temporal information for the full period, it might be impossible to combine the temporal aspects with behavioural features in terms of regression analysis.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, regression and classification analysis were used to eradicate two sets of organisms. According to the results of the model used to predict students' assessment marks, a student's success on a given assignment depends on their grade on a previous assignment within a single course. The researchers come to the conclusion that in a traditional classroom setting, a student's former grade point average (GPA) with a bad mark is viewed as a significant determinant of withdrawal from the next course.

Virtual classes and traditional classrooms both have characteristics that make it more successful to translate past performance into future learning success for students.

According to the final student performance predictor model, a student's use of digital content has a big impact on how well they do throughout the entire course. Due to the removal of temporal factors in the regression analysis, the results also show that long-term student performance achieves superior accuracy than students' assessments grade prediction model. A useful predictor of student performance that is strongly connected with the date that a student deregisters from the course is that date. The data from the regression analysis does not show when the pupils last action occurred before any assessments were taken. The results of the study have recommended that future exams grades be predicted by taking into consideration temporal characteristics.

The use of temporal features for forecasting students' evaluations and grade models is an area of future research. Time series analysis will be performed Using temporal features, and possibly more sophisticated machine learning will be used.

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